

Synthesis of Pyrene Derivatives by Acid-catalysed Decomposition of Bisdiazoketone

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The reaction of α, α' -bis(diazo)-2,2'-biacetophenone (**1**) with $\text{BF}_3\text{-Et}_2\text{O}$ gave 2-(α -hydroxyacetyl)biphenyl-2-acetic acid and its lactone¹. The reactions of **1** with trifluoroacetic acid and with anhydrous stannic chloride are reported in this communication. In each case, 4,9-dihydroxypyrene (**3**) was produced and with trifluoroacetic acid, an intermediate, 4-(α -hydroxyacetyl)-9-hydroxyphenanthrene (**2**) was also obtained. As this procedure is one-step conversion of the bisdiazoketone to 4,9-dihydroxypyrene and the yields are fairly good, it may be used as a suitable method for the preparation of pyrene and its derivatives. Several workers² reported examples of aryl participation in the acid-promoted decompositions of diazoketones.

Treatment of α, α' -bis(diazo)-2,2'-biacetophenone (**1**) with trifluoroacetic acid gave a crude product which on distillation with zinc dust gave pyrene. The separation of the products from the reaction mixture was tedious. The crude reaction products when acetylated with acetic anhydride and pyridine gave 4-(α -acetoxyacetyl)-9-acetoxyphenanthrene and 4,9-diacetoxypyrene. Treatment of **1** with anhydrous stannic chloride yielded only 4,9-dihydroxypyrene which was purified by conversion into 4,9-diacetoxypyrene. 4,9-Diacetoxypyrene when hydrolysed with a mixture of hydrochloric acid and acetic acid gave white amorphous product which was found to be a mixture of 4,9-dihydroxypyrene (**3**) and the tautomeric diketone.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Uv spectra were recorded on a Hitachi U-3400 spectrophotometer, ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Jeol JNM FX-100 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

*Decomposition of α, α' -bis(diazo)-2,2'-biacetophenone (**1**) with trifluoroacetic acid*: The bisdiazoketone **1** (1 g, 3.45 mmol, m.p. 132°)³ in dry dichloromethane (15 ml) was added dropwise to trifluoroacetic acid (15 ml) at -20° under N₂ atmosphere. It was then stirred for 1 h at -20°. Stirring was continued for 3 h more whereupon the temperature gradually rose to 25°. Water (50 ml) was then added to it and heated on a water-bath for 2 h. The reaction mixture was cooled in an ice-water bath, neutralised with solid NaHCO₃ and extracted with ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate extract was washed with saturated NaHCO₃ solution and brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). The crude product (0.69 g) was obtained after evaporation of the solvent: ν_{max} (KBr) 3 500–3 000, 1 690 and 1 605–1 580 cm⁻¹.

Zinc dust distillation of the above crude product gave pyrene (0.47 g, 68%), m.p. 150° (lit.⁴ 149°); λ_{max} (EtOH) 365 (ϵ 2 662), 334 (47 056), 319 (29 795), 305 (12 487), 272 (44 623), 239 (76 117) and 231 nm (53 713). The picrate was obtained as red needles from methanol, m.p. 219° (lit.⁵ m.p. 220°).

4-(α -Acetoxyacetyl)-9-acetoxyphenanthrene and 4,9-diacetoxypyrene: The crude product (0.69 g) from the above reaction was taken in pyridine (10 ml), mixed with acetic anhydride (10 ml) and stirred for 24 h at room

temperature. The solvent was evaporated and then the reaction mixture was cooled in ice, acidified with HCl and extracted with ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate extract was washed with NaHCO₃ solution and brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was evaporated and the residue (0.93 g) was chromatographed on silica gel. The first fraction obtained from ether-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) (1 : 3) eluate gave 4-(α -acetoxyacetyl)-9-acetoxyphenanthrene as a white solid (0.18 g, 16%), which on crystallisations from dichloromethane-petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) afforded fine needles, m.p. 133–34° (Found : C, 71.21; H, 4.92. C₂₀H₁₆O₅ requires : C, 71.42; H, 4.76%); λ_{\max} (dioxane) 340 (ϵ 3 489), 302 (8 916), 276 (15 016) and 255 nm (33 134); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 750, 1 735, 1 690, 1 620, 1 600, 1 565 and 1 485 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 8.92 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 8.81–8.68 (1H, m), 8.36 (1H, s), 8.04–7.60 (5H, m), 5.34 (2H, s), 2.50 (3H, s) and 2.24 (3H, s); *m/z* *M*⁺ 336.

The second fraction obtained from chloroform-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) (3 : 7) eluate gave 4,9-diacetoxypyrene as a yellowish white solid (0.64 g, 58%), which on crystallisations from chloroform-petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) furnished white powder, m.p. 286° (Found : C, 75.32; H, 4.52. C₂₀H₁₄O₄ requires : C, 75.47; H, 4.40%); λ_{\max} (dioxane) 340 (ϵ 33 708), 324 (23 272), 310 (10 754), 276 (39 721), 265 (24 197), 242 (62 155) and 233 nm (39 692); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 750, 1 610, 1 590, 1 490 and 1 445 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 8.31–7.88 (8H, m) and 2.58 (6H, s); *m/z* *M*⁺ 318. The compound was identical with that of the acetylated product of authentic 4,9-dihydroxypyrene⁶. The mixed m.p. showed no depression.

Decomposition of α, α' -bis(diazo)-2,2'-biaceto-phenone (1) with anhydrous stannic chloride : Anhydrous stannic chloride (2.8 g) was added all at a time to a solution of the bisdiazoketone (1; 1 g) in dry dichloromethane (10 ml) at –20° under N₂ atmosphere. It was then stirred for 1h at –20°. The reaction mixture was then acidified with ice-cold HCl (2*N*; 100 ml) and extracted with ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate extract was washed with NaHCO₃ solution and brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). The crude product (0.84 g) was obtained after evaporation of the solvent : ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 500–3 000, 1 690 and 1 605–1 580 cm⁻¹. The crude product was acetylated with acetic anhydride (15 ml)

and pyridine (15 ml) for 24 h at room temperature. The solvent was then evaporated and the residue chromatographed on silica gel. The chloroform-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) (3 : 7) eluate fraction gave a yellowish white solid (0.76 g, 69%), which on crystallisations from chloroform-petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) furnished white powder, m.p. 286°. Spectral data and m.p. of this compound were found to be identical with those of 4,9-diacetoxypyrene, obtained from the previous experiment with trifluoroacetic acid.

4,9-Dihydroxypyrene (3) : A mixture of pure 4,9-diacetoxypyrene (0.34 g, 1.06 mmol; m.p. 286°), acetic acid (9 ml), water (1 ml) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 ml) was refluxed for 6 h at 140–50° under N₂. The reaction mixture was then worked up as usual. It was crystallised from ethyl acetate as white crystals (0.23 g), did not melt upto 300° (Found : C, 81.81; H, 4.42. C₁₆H₁₀O₂ requires : C, 82.05; H, 4.27%); λ_{\max} (dioxane) 382 (ϵ 5 770), 361 (12 377), 343 (20 296), 311 (36 296), 305 (25 132), 280 (19 656), 276 (42 400), 266 (37 241), 257 (42 528⁵) and 245 nm (69 890); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 500–3 000 and 1 695 cm⁻¹

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